

Assessment and Demonstration

Visual assessment

Visual assessment is necessary to quantify how well photovoltaic modules are visually integrated in a building or environment. Novel methods and tools were developed assessing three main criteria: saliency, reflection and colour. The saliency method is a perception based assessment of the visual "change" that a building or environment experiences through a potential BIPV retrofit. The reflection assessment is based on a novel computational simulation method and allows the quantification of the spatio-temporal glare impact of light reflected from BIPV surfaces. The colour assessment quantifies how well the perceived colour of a PV module matches the desired gamut.

Key words: Saliency, perception, reflection, glare, colour

Target audience: Architects & planners, clients and heritage boards

Saliency

The saliency method is a tool used in computer graphics to prioritise areas of visual attention in 2D images for image compression algorithms or in 3D models for level of detail in modelling. Ran Xu analysed several saliency models and transferred the Graph Based Visual Saliency for the first time into the BIPV context, for which several modifications were developed and applied in case studies [1]. The images below show a simplified workflow. Based on two images (existing design and proposed new design with BIPV), her modified saliency method computed the visual difference into a delta map, quantifying the visual impact. This visual impact can be related to regulations, e.g. allowing higher impact in industrial areas and mandating lowest impact for heritage areas [2].

Reflection

The novel computational simulation is based on forward raytracing of sun rays obtained from hourly simulations using weather data, and detailed data obtained from goniophotometric reflection measurements of different BIPV glass properties [3]. Like in the saliency method above, the original and proposed state were modelled in 3D as a base for relative comparison. Here the accumulated annual irradiance "before" and "after" was compared and expressed as falsecolour renderings. The images below, for example, indicate which areas of the site plan are most affected by the reflected irradiance, and thus may experience a glare problem (image left). Further simulations using different glass surface properties revealed that the contrast, and therefore glare probability within this area, can be reduced to an acceptable level (image right).

Colour

The novel colour assessment method is again a relative assessment, this time between a specified colour and the perceived colour when PV glass is printed digitally with ceramic ink. Two corresponding images were compared and their colour difference computed according to CIE standards. This objective difference was then validated through experiments with human observers [4]. In a second step, more than 1'000 colours were specified and printed on glass, and assembled as coloured PV modules. Using the above method, the gamuts of the specified and perceived colours were compared. The black dots in the image below show the colour coordinates of the specified colours, while the coloured dots show those of the printed colours as they appear with different glass types (clear and satinated) and ceramic ink volumes (pl). This indicates a reduced colour gamut for digitally printed coloured PV modules [5].

References

- [1] Xu, Ran (2016). Visual Impact assessment of BIPV in building retrofits using saliency methods. [PhD Thesis EPFL](#)
- [2] Xu, Ran et al. (2017). Quantitative Evaluation of BIPV Visual Impact in Building Retrofits using Saliency Models. [Energies 2017 \(10/5\)](#)
- [3] Schregle, et al. (2018). Spatio-Temporal Visualisation of Reflections from Building Integrated Photovoltaics. [Buildings, 8\(8\)](#).
- [4] Schregle, et al. (2017). Computational Colour Matching of Laminated Photovoltaic Modules for Building Envelopes. [Buildings, 7\(3\)](#).
- [5] Schregle, et al. (2018). An Image-Based Gamut Analysis of Translucent Digital Ceramic Prints for Coloured Photovoltaic Modules. [Buildings, 8\(2\)](#).